

Knowledge Attitude and Practice of Occupationally Exposed Persons to Bovine Tuberculosis in Kumasi, Ghana

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Abstract: Bovine tuberculosis (bTB) continues to be a serious public health concern, particularly in developing nations such as Ghana. It is most frequently found during meat inspection at the abattoir or slaughterhouse, and it is also occasionally found during sporadic disease screening. A total of 150 participants which included butchers, farmers, veterinarians, workers and staff of the abattoir, meat buyers and sellers were selected by simple random sampling. An interviewer administered pretested structured questionnaire was used to collect data on the socio-demographic profiles and knowledge, attitude as well as practices of abattoir workers on Bovine tuberculosis in Kumasi Abattoir, Ghana. From the questionnaire survey, 96.8% of the males and 70.0 % of the females knew that humans can contact tuberculosis from animals and knew at least one mode of tuberculosis transmission. Furthermore, 100% of respondents between the ages of 19 to 39 years also agreed that it was important that they protect themselves as they handle animals and their products

Keywords: *Bovine tuberculosis, abattoir, humans, public health, Ghana*

Introduction

Bovine tuberculosis is an important zoonotic disease because it is transmissible to man through aerosol and ingestion of contaminated meat and unpasteurised milk (which often leads to extra-pulmonary infections) (Office International des Epizooties, 2009). The disease is present in almost all African countries (Ayele *et al.*, 2004). It is known to be prevalent in about

33 (80%) of the 43 African member countries of the regional commission of the Office International des Epizooties (Daborn *et al.*, 1994). Bovine tuberculosis is considered to be among the seven highly neglected zoonotic diseases of the world and has a major impact on international trade of animal products (Sahraoui *et al.* 2009).

Human's susceptibility to Bovine TB poses great health risk especially to consumers of beef and raw milk as well as veterinarians, livestock workers and abattoir workers. This is because TB caused by *M. bovis* is clinically indistinguishable from TB caused by *M. tuberculosis* (Ayele *et al.*, 2004). The zoonotic importance constitutes an important public health problem (Thoen *et al.*, 2006). Human TB of animal origin, particularly that caused by *M. bovis* has become more important since the emergence of HIV/AIDS (O Reilly and Daborn, 1995; WHO, 2021).

Abattoir and livestock workers may acquire Bovine TB by inhaling cough spray or aerosols from infected cattle and may develop typical pulmonary TB. Such patients may infect cattle, though evidence of human to human transmission is subjective and unreliable. There is increasing contact between humans and animals worldwide due to increasing population density and growth, especially in poor developing countries where livestock offers important socioeconomic, cultural, and religious pathways out of poverty (OIE, 2017.) Animal and human TB are both emerging and re-emerging. They are both caused by pathogenic bacteria of the *M. tuberculosis* complex (MTC) including *M. bovis* and *M. tuberculosis* (OIE, 2008); they are widespread in Africa and affect the

animal industries and human health (Ayele, *et al* 2004). Again, there is the problem of Bovine TB whose numerical contribution to the general TB burden is unknown (Ayele *et al.*, 2004). Bovine TB has been controlled and managed in most developed countries due to the implementation of the test and slaughter (TS) policy of all infected cattle and compensation of affected farmers by governments.

In most developing nations with higher disease prevalence, zoonotic tuberculosis caused by *Mycobacterium bovis* (*M. bovis*), has drawn more attention as a public health danger. It has the capacity to infect a variety of hosts, including a variety of domestic animals, particularly cattle, and a wide array of wildlife reservoirs. *M. bovis* can inadvertently infect humans through the aerosol inhalation of infectious droplets, infected bodily fluids, or contaminated tissues in the presence of wounds from infected animals. These animal handlers comprising of livestock farmers, abattoir workers, veterinarians and their assistants, hunters, wildlife workers as well as other animal handlers are at different risk of contracting *M. bovis* infection, depending on the nature of their jobs and how close is their interaction with infected animals. Devi *et al.* , 2021). Very importantly, TB is one of the three primary diseases of poverty alongside HIV/AIDS and malaria (WHO, 2021) and therefore is

of major global and public health importance.

Bovine TB is mostly only detected at slaughter during meat inspection and occasionally during sporadic screening for the disease. People who attend to, and in close contact with cattle such as herdsmen, butchers and veterinarians as well as the general public that consume fresh milk or infected meat are exposed to Bovine TB (Bilal *et al.*, 2010). *M. bovis* has been isolated from sputum and tissue samples from humans especially among the Fulani herdsmen with or without clinical signs of tuberculous in Nigeria (Abubakar *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, Cadmus and others in Nigeria indicated that a higher prevalence of bovine TB in cattle owned by tuberculous patients was found than in cattle owned by non-tuberculous owners, which suggests the significant role of *M. bovis* in the incidence of tuberculosis in humans (Cadmus *et al.*, 2022).

The occurrence of *M. bovis* in humans against the background of the soaring HIV/AIDS incidence in Eastern and Southern Africa implies that the risk of spill-over of zoonotic bovine TB to rural communities is rapidly increasing. Thus, the correlation between the prevalence of *M. bovis* infection in humans and that of local cattle populations highlights the potential threat of this disease for humans especially

in developing countries, where drinking raw milk is a common practice in rural areas in particular (Cosivi *et al.*, 2006).

According to a study conducted in Ghana at the Korle -bu Teaching Hospital on sputum samples from TB patients, 3% were bovine TB (Addo *et al.*, 2001). This result called for the need to conduct a nationwide survey using both conventional and molecular techniques to characterize various mycobacteria species causing TB in Ghana, to know the various strains circulating in the country (Addo *et al.*, 2001).

Lack of knowledge about Bovine TB infection among cattle farmers exposes them to the disease as demonstrated by Kang'ethe and others in their study to determine the prevalence of Bovine TB and possible risk factors for human infection in Kenya, it was found out that 57% of the respondents from dairy farms and 72% from non-farming households had limited knowledge of bovine TB and this made them unable to take measures to protect themselves from contracting the disease. The main risk factors identified were being a milk processor, distance between cattle kraals and houses as well as the time spent attending to cattle (Kang'ethe *et al.*, 2007). Zoonotic transmission of bovine TB was also established in a case study carried out

on a 29-year-old hunter in 2004 that got injured with his knife when he was dressing an infected deer. The bovine TB strain in both the deer and the hunter were the same. The investigation of the infection in the case patient provided strong evidence of

transmission of *M. bovis* infection from deer to human through percutaneous injection with a contaminated hunting knife (Wilkins *et al.*, 2007).

Figure 1: Tuberculous lesions in the lung of a four year old cow (Credit: authors)

Study Area

Cross sectional study was conducted between June 2016 and July 2016 in Ghana, Kumasi abattoir. Kumasi Abattoir Company Limited (Latitude 6.662°N, Longitude 1.615°W) was set up to replace the local slaughter house formerly known as Mayanka. It is an ultra-modern abattoir built by Canadian experts to meet the standards of the western abattoir. The company was officially commissioned on the 24th July 1998. The abattoir provides the daily beef requirements of the inhabitants of Kumasi and neighboring cities. It has slaughter and dressing capacity of 400 cattle, 300 sheep and goats and 100 pigs per day.

Data Collection

Structured questionnaires were administered to participants who gave their consent including butchers, farmers, veterinarians, workers and staff of the abattoir, meat buyers and sellers.

Ethical clearance for this study was sort from the appropriate authorities in Ghana.

Data Analysis

At the $p < 0.05$ level of significance, descriptive statistics like percentages were examined using Chi-square.

Results

Demographics

The age range of all respondents was from 20 to over 50 years (Table 1). The number of male participants was higher with 86.3% and female had a percentage of 13.7%. More than half of the respondents had only primary education with 56.1%, followed by secondary education with 17.8%, tertiary 16.4% and those with no formal education at all being 9.5%. Also, 57.3% of the respondents live in high density areas and 36.9% in medium density areas and finally 5.48% in low density areas.

Table 1: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of respondents.

s/n	variables	Percentage %	
1	How old were you as at your last birthday?	20-29 years	21.9
		30-39 years	30.1
		40-49 years	26.0
		Above 50 years	21.9
2	Sex of respondent	Male	86.3

		Female	13.7
3	Religion	Christianity	13.7
		Islam	86.3
4	Marital status	Single	32.9
		Married	58.9
		Others	8.2
5	Highest level of education	None	9.5
		Primary	56.1
		Secondary	17.8
		Tertiary	16.4
6	Area of city lived in.	High density area	57.3
		Medium density area	36.9
		Low density area	5.48
7	How many on average live together in a room	1 person	23.3
		2-3 persons	64.4
		More than 3 persons	12.3

Awareness and knowledge of bovine tuberculosis among abattoir workers in Kumasi Ghana

When respondents were asked if they knew how TB was transmitted, their age, and the period or duration spent in business did not significantly affect their knowledge of TB transmission while gender and academic status did (Table 2). Though no female respondent believed that TB can be transmitted through milk and milk products, 35.6% of males agreed on that. 70.0% of females agreed that TB can be transmitted

by direct contact when compared to 54.6% of males and 9.6% of males agreed that TB can be transmitted through aerosol compared to 30.0% of the female respondents.

No significant relationship exists between age, gender, academic status, as well as duration in business and the respondents' knowledge of TB signs and symptoms. Ages 30- 39 answered yes if they believed TB can be cured with 86.4% and ages 20-29 answered no with 53.7% (Table 2).

Table 2: Awareness and knowledge of tuberculosis among abattoir workers in Kumasi Ghana

Variable	Diseases can be transmitted from animals to humans		Humans can contact TB from animals		How is TB transmitted?			Knowing the clinical signs of TB		Knowing TB can be cured	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Direct Contact	Meat and Milk products	Aerosol	Yes	No	Yes	No
Age	#		#		#			#		*	
20 – 29	100	0	81.3	18.7	56.3	18.7	25	75	25	56.3	53.7
30 – 39	100	0	95.5	4.5	59.1	36.4	4.5	59.1	40.9	86.4	13.6
40 – 49	100	0	100	0	47.4	47.4	5.2	52.6	47.4	57.9	42.1
≥ 50	93.8	6.2	93.8	6.2	62.5	18.8	18.7	56.3	43.7	81.3	18.7
Gender	#		*		*			#		#	
Male	98.4	1.6	96.8	3.2	54	36.5	9.6	57.1	42.9	69.8	30.2
Female	100	0	70	30	70	0	30	80	20	80	20
Education Status	#		#		*			#		#	
None	100	0	85.7	14.3	71.4	14.3	14.3	85.7	14.3	57.1	43.9
Primary	97.6	2.4	92.7	7.3	56.1	41.5	2.4	53.7	46.3	73.2	27.8
Secondary	100	0	92.3	7.7	69.2	23.1	7.7	61.5	38.5	69.2	30.8
Tertiary	100	0	100	0	33.3	16.7	50	66.7	33.3	75	25
Duration in Business	#		#		#			#		#	
> 9 years	100	0	87.9	12.1	63.6	24.2	12.1	66.7	33.3	69.7	30.3
10 – 19 years	100	0	100	0	39.1	47.8	13.1	56.5	43.5	65.2	34.8
≥ 20 years	94.1	5.9	94.1	5.9	64.7	23.5	11.8	52.9	47.1	82.4	17.6

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Attitude and Practices of abattoir workers to bovine tuberculosis in Kumasi Ghana

There was no significant relationship between age, gender, academic status, as well as duration in business and the

importance of protecting themselves while handling slaughtered animals and their products (Table 3) (Table 4). Responses to questions on practices showed that 76.7% of them would do this through the use of protective materials such as overall and hand gloves, 10.9% through limited contact with animals and animal products and

12.3% through frequent hand washing. The high percentage of those that believe in good hygiene practices can be attributed to the fact that most of the respondents are butchers who use protective clothing as part of their work clothes which include boots and long aprons.

Table 3: Attitude of abattoir workers to bovine tuberculosis.

	Is it dangerous to work with animal?		Why do you think it is dangerous?		Is it important to protect yourself while handling slaughtered animals and products?	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Age	#		*		#	
20 – 29	93.7	6.3	68.8	31.2	100.0	0.0
30 – 39	95.5	4.5	50.0	50.0	100.0	0.0
40 – 49	94.7	5.3	31.6	68.4	94.7	5.3
≥ 50	93.8	6.3	68.8	31.2	100.0	0.0
Gender	#		*		#	
Male	93.7	6.3	52.4	47.6	98.4	1.6
Female	100.0	0.0	60.0	40.0	100.0	0.0
Education Status	#		*		#	
None	100.0	0.0	71.4	28.6	100.0	0.0
Primary	95.1	4.9	46.3	53.7	97.6	2.4
Secondary	92.3	7.7	38.5	61.5	100.0	0.0
Tertiary	91.7	8.3	83.3	16.7	100.0	0.0
Duration in Business	#		#		#	
> 9 years	93.9	6.1	57.6	42.4	96.9	3.1
10 – 19 years	95.7	4.3	39.1	60.9	100.0	0.0

≥ 20 years	94.1	5.9	64.7	35.3	100.0	0.0
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***Significant at P≤0.05**

Not significant at P≤0.05

Table 4: Practices of the abattoir workers about tuberculosis

Variable	Ways of protection from animals infections			Where to go for treatment if infected with TB		What type of hygienic practice observed to protect against TB infection		
	Preventive Medicine	Good hygienic practices	Prayer	Modern Medicine	Traditional	Protective materials	Limited contact	Washing of hands
Age	#			#		#		
20 – 29	18.8	81.3	0.0	93.8	6.2	68.8	18.8	12.5
30 – 39	4.5	90.9	4.5	95.5	4.5	72.7	13.6	13.7
40 – 49	0.0	89.5	10.5	100.0	0.0	89.5	5.3	5.2
≥ 50	0.0	93.8	6.2	100.0	0.0	81.3	0.0	18.8
Gender	*			#		*		
Male	3.2	92.1	4.7	96.8	3.2	87.3	1.6	11.1
Female	20.0	70.0	10.0	100.0	0.0	20.0	60.0	20.0
Education Status	#			#		*		
None	14.3	85.7	0.0	100.0	0.0	57.1	0.0	42.9
Primary	2.4	92.7	4.9	95.1	4.9	82.9	12.2	4.9
Secondary	0.0	84.6	15.4	100.0	0.0	76.9	15.4	7.7
Tertiary	16.7	83.3	0.0	100.0	0.0	75.0	0.0	25.0
Duration in Business	#			#		*		
> 9 years	12.1	84.9	3.0	96.9	3.1	66.7	21.2	12.1
10 – 19 years	0.0	91.3	8.7	95.7	4.3	91.3	0.0	8.7
≥ 20 years	0.0	94.1	5.9	100.0	0.0	82.4	0.0	17.6

***Significant at P≤0.05**

Not significant at P≤0.05

Discussion

Though our findings show that the occupationally exposed in Kumasi Abattoir had good knowledge about Bovine TB, there is still the need for public health enlightenment programs regarding food hygiene practices particularly among abattoir workers. In the same vein, the general public should also be educated on the dangers of consuming meat, milk and their products from Bovine TB infected cattle.

The occupationally exposed people in Kumasi abattoir had knowledge about Bovine TB and the different modes of transmission. Persons at risk should be identified and appropriate control measures put in place, public health enlightenment programs on food hygiene practices should be carried out routinely among the abattoir workers and those at risk. In the same vein, the general public should also be educated on the dangers of consuming meat, milk and their products from Bovine TB infected cattle

Conclusion

Prevalence data on TB in animals in most developing countries are generally scarce. This study serves as a source of active surveillance data on the Bovine TB as well as help target abattoir

workers and veterinarians as a high risk group for TB screening. This study strengthened the “One Health” approach in the prevention and control of TB in Ghana and hopefully provide empirical data for future work in other West African countries.

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